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PHILANTHROPY IN INDIA

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PHILANTHROPY IN INDIA

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ABSTRACT

Philanthropy in India is as old as India itself. It originates from religions that have practiced giving for the longest time. This working paper investigates individual philanthropy, and corporate Philanthropy, the trends of both of them and regulatory changes in India. The specific regulations looked at are the refusal of Foreign Aid, the Foreign Contributions (Regulations) Act, Section 135 of the Companies Act 2013, Income Tax Act 1961, the Trusts Act 1882, and the amendments that have been made to them. The paper uses mainly secondary data such as research papers, articles and reports and accompanies the text with primary data from the talk series at CDPP "Philanthropy in India". The results found was that individual giving and corporate philanthropy have been increasing. For both, the most common cause for philanthropic donations were related to religious purposes, education and healthcare. The regulatory changes restrictive in the case of FCRA, while for the others, there were both benefits and limitations. The next step is to look to the future, investigate what lies ahead for Philanthropy in India after the pandemic and the recent regulatory changes reaching out to the grassroots while looking for ways to improve philanthropy's efficiency and efficacy.

1. INTRODUCTION: DEFINING PHILANTHROPY IN INDIA

Philanthropy is a word that has many definitions. The current western understanding of this word comes from the 18th century. Individuals and the state started to take on the duty of care and welfare of the less fortunate, a function formerly handled by religious authorities (Singh, 2002). However, the original meaning of philanthropy was love for humankind (Singh, 2002). This broad definition of philanthropy can be interpreted differently by each person and in each country. However, a commonality that can be gathered from all definitions is that philanthropy is about giving and giving can come in various forms.

Philanthropy in India is rooted in its religions coming from diverse cultures and traditions. Globally and in India, Philanthropy has been on the rise, and trends have emerged. Various reports have attempted to keep track of the data and numbers involved in philanthropy. To know India's position in philanthropy compared to other countries, a helpful index to look at is the World Giving Index by Charities Aid Foundation (CAF). In 2021, India is a generous giver at rank 14 out of 114 countries (CAF, 2021). With philanthropy on the rise, research into it has also been increasing in India. This working paper will focus on corporate and individual Philanthropy in India, its trends, and the regulatory changes that have affected Philanthropy in India. The specific regulatory changes that will be explored are the refusal of Foreign Aid, the Foreign Contributions (Regulations) Act, Section 135 of the Companies Act 2013, Income Tax Act 1961, the Trusts Act 1882, and the amendments that have been made to them.

2. THE AGE-OLD TRADITION OF GIVING IN INDIA

Philanthropy in India has been prominent since ancient times. Giving came naturally to the country's people as it was inscribed in religious texts and had become a part of the tradition. On the other hand, corporate philanthropy came a little later and has become prominent in India in recent years. It can be traced back to the founding of the Tata Group in 1868, which established the first philanthropic trust of India, the JN Tata Endowment in 1892 (Candid, 2021). This marked the beginning of corporates involvement in Philanthropy in India. However, the first form of giving in India would come under the category of Individual giving, described in the next section.

2.1 The idea of giving is ingrained in Indians through religion

Individual giving includes a wide range of givers. It consists of a person who has given Rs. Two hundred on a crowdfunding platform to support a child's education includes a person who has donated Rs. 200 crores to the health industry. The range of people included in individual giving is vast, making it challenging to keep track. The distinction between the 'small' givers and the 'large' ones is that the small givers often come under retail philanthropy. In contrast, the significant givers are High Net-Worth Individuals (HNIs) and usually come under family philanthropy.

Figure 1 : Roots of religious giving

Individual giving is as old as India, one could say. It has been emphasised upon across religions. In Hinduism, giving is dana, a part of one's dharma, a religious duty (Sugirtharajah, 2001). According to dharma, the person's wealth should be used to give back, both at home to extended family and beyond the home (Sugirtharajah, 2001). Moreover, the Bhagavadgita mentions three types of giving, which overall say that any kind of giving motivated by selfishness is not of value (Sugirtharajah, 2001). The Bhagavadgita also talks about how people with abundance must share it with others (Sanjay, 2014). In Islam, charity is called by two names, Sadaqah and Zakat ("What is Sadaqah...", 2021). Zakat is an obligatory type of charity, while Sadaqah is a voluntary charity that brings a range of benefits to the givers and receivers ("What is Sadaqah...", 2021). Christianity has tithing, giving 10% of their earnings as a type of tax to the Church (Cambridge Dictionary, 2021). Sikhism also has a giving like a Tithe, called dhasvandh, where the person gives 10% of their earnings in the name of their Guru or spiritual force (Sikh Dharma International, 2021).

The Gita emphasises that one should give at bad times, usually during famines. Another principle is that only people in need should be given; this is similar to our modern principle of accountability. The most direct donation is food; it says that you have excess food, you should give it to people who do not have enough. Religious donation at temples was also encouraged. The giving away of clothes and labour as volunteers are also encouraged. The labour donation is practised by the Sikhs today. Donation of knowledge was also encouraged; the texts say that a guru should donate all his knowledge before he dies. In the Upanishads, the giving patterns in India were very specific. The principle of giving was based on "dhanam" (philanthropy). It was based on the principles of "desh", 'kaal' and "patra". "Desh" was the region in need; Kaal; was the time of hunger, such as famine and patra; was duty. Giving wealth to a region or a state where people needed money to rebuild their lives.

There have been two forms of giving, sacrificial (Istha) and secular (Purtha). The secular form was Building of Dharamshala's and Sarai's in religious places, work done in drought relief and providing water for travellers, digging of wells and tanks, feeding birds and cows, care of animals. Many merchants established dharmada charity and set apart a portion of their profits. The Religious form was to offer sacrifices to the Gods and the temple.

The word "charity" was first described by the Christians; the word came from the Latin word 'Charitas' roughly meaning "love for others". Saint Paul wrote to his followers that they must give to others to express their love towards others. In Christianity, Tithe is when the 10% of income given to the Church is also philanthropic activity. In addition to Tithe, Christianity encourages to give anonymously. In St Luke, Christ says, "What you do to the least of them you do unto Me".

In Islam, the most important terms are Sadaqa and Zakat. Sadaqa has been interpreted in the more restricted sense of voluntary rather than obligatory giving (Quran 9: 104-5) links God's acceptance of repentance with Sadaqa, thus suggesting its value as an expiation.

Zakat is obligatory giving (2.5% of income, including money and total wealth consisting of property, cattle etc.). Giving is also associated with reward from God (Quran 2:245) "which through God's bounty will be multiplied many times over". There is also another ancillary type of charity known as Fidiya, a type of fine given when one fails to fast in the month of Ramadan, hence also serving as an expiation.

In Sikhism, philanthropy is mainly done through Dasvandh and Kar Seva. Following the Dasvandh, Sikhs donate 10% of their income to the Gurudwara. Kar Seva refers to the obligatory donation of one's services to the Gurudwara; this includes performing manual labour.

Religious giving is about the highest in the world. In the USA, religious giving accounts for 35%, whereas in India, around 80% of all philanthropy is religious. Indians give predominantly for religious purposes and not much (15%) for other purposes. The religious promise of expiation seems to be a significant motivator. A religious person giving can expect his sins to be forgiven; a secular person can only expect an ATG receipt (Cherian, 2014).

The four most common religions in India all mention giving. Individual giving can be considered a tradition in India, and it has been drilled into Indians since childhood. For example, Mr Manzoor Ghori, the executive Director of Indian Muslim Relief & Charities (IMRC), revealed that his motivation for entering the philanthropy sector was because his mother had ingrained giving since childhood and giving came naturally to him as a result.

Giving in India has developed as the years and technology progressed. Now, the distance between givers and recipients is gradually decreasing as online giving is becoming more popular. For example, crowdfunding allows any individual to donate to a wide variety of causes and allows donations of any amount. According to the Everyday Giving in India report by Sattva, the total individual giving in India is 5 billion dollars, and 90% of this is informal (Kejriwal, 2019). The formal individual giving is 10%, which goes to non-profits, and is part of retail Philanthropy (Kejriwal, 2019). The report also says that this is growing both online and offline by 30% and 25%, respectively (Kejriwal, 2019). The closing of the distance between givers and recipients has given a boost to individual philanthropy.

Individual giving is also a large part of private philanthropy in India and has increased in recent years. According to Bain's India Philanthropy Report 2017, from 2011 to 2016, there was a 44% growth in

individual philanthropy, and this growth was mainly responsible for the 50% share increase in private funds in India (Sheth et al., 2017). Individual philanthropy has been rising as more Indians are becoming wealthier (Sheth et al., 2017). By the year 2018, individual philanthropy grew by 21% (Sheth et al., 2019). The 2019 Bain report on Philanthropy in India said that individual philanthropists have a critical role in the development of India and achieving the 2030 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) (Sheth et al., 2019). According to the most recent Bain report in 2021, private funding had increased by 23% from 2019 to 2020, and out of this, individual philanthropy grew by 48% (Sheth et al., 2021). Specifically, retail philanthropy, which the report took as donations less than INR 5 crores, was 28% and family philanthropy and HNIs were 20% (Sheth et al., 2021). Individual giving in India has played a significant role in the growth of private Philanthropy in India.

Since individual giving includes a wide range of donors and receivers, it is challenging to keep track of. However, one thing is sure: individual giving in India has grown every year in recent years. Its roots lie in the religions that have instilled the tradition of giving in individuals. It has evolved and developed with time, now including various ways to bring together givers and receivers under a cause.

2.2 What is the role of corporates in giving?

Eventually, corporate philanthropy became the talk of the town in India and was growing since it was introduced in India. A revolutionary change made to corporate philanthropy was the introduction of the Companies Act in 2013. It was a turning point since it made corporate social responsibility (CSR) compulsory for companies, and India was the first and only country to do so. Hence, the discourse around corporate Philanthropy in India is divided into two distinct eras, before and after the Companies Act 2013. The below representation shows a timeline of the changes in corporate giving in India.

Figure 2: Timeline of the changes in corporate giving in India

The corporate philanthropy era before mandated CSR was led by the idea of trusteeship. Around World War one, Gandhi's introduction of the concept of 'trusteeship' was welcomed by prominent corporate leaders such as Jamnala Bajaj and GD Birla (Godfrey et al., 2017). CSR, before independence, was led by pioneers of industrialisation, namely Bajaj, Tata, Godrej, and Birla (Chandra, n.d.). They pushed forward CSR by establishing health and education institutions, charitable foundations, and trusts for the development of the community (Chandra, n.d.). During the independence movement, Gandhi had introduced trusteeship and urged these wealthy industrialists to donate their wealth to the marginalised and poor in society (Chandra, n.d.). His trusteeship model encouraged these large, rich corporates to give back to society and aid in the development of the underprivileged community of society as it was part of their social responsibility ("Social Responsibility of...", 2021). By introducing the idea that corporates were just as responsible as an institution for developing the Indian society, accountability and responsibility were placed on them. This opened up a space for corporates in the world of philanthropic giving.

Then came the 1990s with liberalisation, privatisation, and globalisation (LPG) of the Indian economy. A new generation of corporate leaders, such as Infosys and Wipro, had shown a strong desire to contribute their riches towards social development (Ramachandran et al., 2009). Family foundations and trusts grew during this period as many wealthy individuals set up private foundations for Philanthropy (Ramachandran et al., 2009). CSR in this period also included NGO sponsorship and private-public partnerships (Deo, 2015).

With the rapid economic growth in the 1990s resulting from LPG, income inequality also increased, increasing the divide between the rich and the poor. This pushed corporates to get more involved in CSR and address these social issues (Deo, 2015). The need for corporate philanthropy increased during this time, and the establishment of family foundations also grew.

Finally, corporate philanthropy faced its most significant change in 2013 when the Companies Act was introduced and mandated 2% CSR for corporates. The bill of 2009 that introduced the idea of mandated CSR was formulated much earlier, back in 1993 (Mukherjee & Chaturvedi, 2013). This proposal, at that time, was not clear in many areas, such as what counts as CSR expenditures, and it did not have an enforcement mechanism (Mukherjee & Chaturvedi, 2013). Later, provisions were added to the bill making it more explicit. Eventually, it became part of the Companies Act in 2013, under section 135. This section continues to dictate corporate Philanthropy in India. The mandatory CSR regulations are discussed in section 4.3.

CSR and corporate philanthropy have gone through quite a few changes in India. First, trusteeship was introduced where large, wealthy companies were asked to share part of their wealth with the poor and underprivileged community as part of CSR. Next, due to LPG and India's rapid economic growth, family foundations and trusts grew. The increase in income inequality led to more focus on combatting these issues through CSR. Lastly, mandated CSR was introduced, which yet again changed the course of corporate Philanthropy in India.

3. PHILANTHROPY SECTOR TRENDS

As philanthropy has been growing, trends have emerged across the sector. This section focuses on the growth of philanthropy and the top causes that donors donate. The data gathered will answer how much philanthropy and philanthropic giving have grown and the areas/sectors that receive more.

3.1 How has corporate philanthropy played out?

Corporate philanthropy is a large part of philanthropy worldwide and has been going on for many years. Worldwide trends seem to be similar to the trends of corporate Philanthropy in India. CECP's Giving in Numbers data show trends from surveying around 500+ companies (CECP, 2021). In almost all the reports (2015-2020), the top causes and order were the same. The leading causes were education at number one, health and social services at number two, and community and economic development at the third. The only year this was not in that order was 2020, where the top cause was healthcare, the second was community, and economic development and education came in last.

A reasonable explanation for this change would be the pandemic caused by Covid-19, which has increased the need for improved healthcare and repair the hit taken by the economy. It would explain why the top cause for corporate philanthropic donations is healthcare in 2020, and the second is community and economic development. Another trend is that giving has been increasing for corporates.

According to CECP's report in 2017, 48% of the companies reported an increase in giving by 2.3% between 2013-16 (Good Returns, 2018). The same report also said that these companies planned to donate the same amount or more in the coming years. In CECP's 2018 report, total giving had increased, giving a total of \$25.7 billion from 2016-18 (McClimon, 2020). So far, one can confirm that corporate giving has grown. The areas that receive the most philanthropic money from corporates are the education, health, and community and economic development sectors.

The trends for corporate Philanthropy in India are not vastly different from the global trends. However, corporate Philanthropy in India has been different from the rest of the world since 2013 as it is the only country with mandated corporate social responsibility (CSR) for companies.

The graph in figure 3 below shows the total amount spent through contributions by corporates on sectors. The top two causes are education and healthcare, which is in line with the global trends. Moreover, the leading cause in every year from 2014 to 2019 has been education, the same as global trends. Education seems to be a priority across the world. However, there is a reason for concern with this scenario since the development of a country requires funds in various parts of the development sector. However, the trends show that the funds through philanthropy are diverted towards healthcare and education. An insight given by Mr Manzoor Ghori is that "do not expect everybody to do everything" when he was asked how could one find the money for more minor causes such as music, arts and culture. Despite the focus on healthcare and education in corporate giving, organisations interested in other 'minority' causes will give to those causes regardless of the trends.

Figure 3: Total amount spent on different development sectors 2014-2019

Source: (Centre for Social Impact and Philanthropy (CSIP), 2021)

The pie chart in figure 4 below shows the CSR amount spent from 2014-2019 combined. Throughout the years, donations to education take up 52%, and healthcare is second with 26%. The rest of the sectors have much lower percentages in comparison. The pie chart demonstrates the skewed distribution of corporate Philanthropy in India.

Figure 4: CSR amount spent on each development sector 2014-2019

Source: (CSIP, 2021)

Figure 5 below shows the growth rate of the total amount of contributions by corporate. The growth rate fell from 2015-16 to 2016-17, but the growth rate increased. It is different from the global trends where giving from corporates has been rising since 2013.

Figure 5: Growth rate of the total amount of contributions (%) / 2014-2019

Source: (CSIP, 2021)

Mathew Cherian, Chairperson of CARE India and Author, observes that CSR grants have been concentrated around the well-developed areas within a state, usually near the donor companies headquarters. Also, the CSR funds were going to more prosperous states and not to poorer states. Even in the more prosperous states, the funds are given to wealthier areas where the industries are located.

For example, In Maharashtra, the districts of Pune and Mumbai (suburban) received upward of INR 200 Cr. each in CSR funding. In contrast, Hingoli, Jalna, Buldhana and Parbhani received less than INR 1 Cr. Deficits in funding were also observed in the tribal areas and a disparity that NGOs in the Ranchi consultation emphasised. As per NGOs in Bangalore consultation, Northern Karnataka (e.g., Gulbarga) receives lesser CSR funds than Bangalore, given the operational presence of corporates in the city. In addition to the uneven distribution of funds, there has been no emphasis on the planet, sustainability, or ethical profits. Also, the categories of donations were very uneven, with education taking a large part of the donation and other issues such as human rights and gender equality getting very paltry sums.

Overall corporate philanthropy trends in India are mainly similar to global trends. However, with India as the only country with mandated CSR, the story of corporate philanthropy is different than with other countries. As for the causes that get the most contribution, education has been in the top spot all the time, except in 2020, when the pandemic forced funds to be diverted towards healthcare. The data for India is not yet available, but it can be safely assumed that similar results will be seen.

3.2 Is individual giving on the rise?

Philanthropy includes individuals' donations and contributions and makes up a large part of philanthropic contributions. Whether an average salary person donating to a cause or a billionaire contributing to a cause, it all comes under individual giving. Individual giving worldwide has been increasing as time goes on (World Food Programme, n.d.).

Worldwide trends for individual giving are given in a report by Nonprofit Tech for Good, which surveyed 23,609 donors over three years (2020). It is found that the top cause for giving by individuals was children and youth in 2017 and 2018. It changed in 2020, and the top cause was hunger and homelessness. As for corporate philanthropy trends in 2020, this change in cause could be because of the pandemic. The pandemic has worsened economic situations and poverty worldwide, with millions of people losing their jobs and getting infected. Hence, hunger and homelessness being the top cause make sense to a certain extent. This brings up why health and wellness were not the top cause, but this cause tied with children and youth in second place.

Moreover, the percentage difference is only 1 per cent between the top cause and the second cause. Contrary to the global corporate philanthropy trends, individual giving does not focus on education as much. In 2017 and 2018, education placed seventh, and in 2020 it was tenth. For individual givers, children and the youth, and health seem to be much higher on the priority list than education, whose position has lowered from 2018 to 2020 (Nonprofit Tech for Good, 2020). So individual giving across the world has been growing, and the top causes were receiving the most philanthropic money from individual donors are the youth and health.

In India, individual giving has been increasing. According to Bain's report on Philanthropy in India in 2020, the percentage of individual contributions as a share of private funding grew from 26% to 60% (Seth et al., 2020). A survey done by GiveIndia has also found that individual giving is increasing in India (. TET Bureau, 2020). This is similar to the global trend. As shown in the graph in figure 6 below, in recent years, from 2018 to 2020, individual giving from the top 10 philanthropists of each year has grown.

Figure 5: Growth rate of the total amount of contributions (%)/ 2014-2019

Source: (CSIP, 2021)

As for the top causes for individual giving in India, the trends differ from the global trends. In India, similar to corporate philanthropy, the leading cause was education in all the years of the data. As the graph in figure 7 below shows, total contributions between the top cause of education and second cause of healthcare had a significant gap in all the years. The contributions for education have been gradually increasing and suddenly shot up in 2020 to 9,324 crores. On the other hand, healthcare has been much lower in comparison, even in the year 2020. Overall, in India, the trend has been that individual giving is increasing, and the cause receiving the most philanthropic money from individual givers are education and health.

Figure 7: Total contributions for the top 2 causes (INR crore) / 2016-2020

Source: (CSIP, 2021)

In conclusion, the trends worldwide for individual giving are not entirely the same as the trends in India. The cause for individual giving differs; in India, the top cause is education, and globally the top cause is children and youth. One common trend is that individual giving has been increasing over the years.

4. REGULATORY CHANGES OF PHILANTHROPY IN INDIA

Looking at the trends of philanthropic giving, the questions of is it growing and which causes get the most money from this giving were answered. India has seen many regulatory changes that impacted the philanthropic sector. These regulations guide the flow of philanthropic money and control it. They may even be able to affect the trends of growth of philanthropic money with increased restrictions. India's voluntary sector (VO) is governed by a complex legal framework that comprises multiple central and state laws that govern three aspects of a VO's existence: registration, taxation, and regulatory compliances. Many of these laws overlap and intersect in myriad ways and have undergone multiple amendments with varied state-level enforcement mechanisms. This section explores the regulations India has placed on the sector. To a certain extent, it tries to answer questions such as - Is regulation for philanthropy needed? Could the philanthropic sector do better without these regulations? How far have these regulations impacted philanthropy?

4.1 The refusal of foreign aid in India

India has a long history of being a recipient of foreign aid. In the earlier half of the 1990s, India received an average annual aid of 2.9 billion dollars (Jha & Swaroop, 1999). There was a change in the 2000s, with India transitioning into a giver of aid rather than a receiver. According to a newspaper article from The Hindu, there are five arguments for India refusing to receive foreign aid, summarised in the diagram below (Jacob, 2018). The first is that policies in India justify refusing foreign aid. It is argued that in 2004 a policy was set up that said India should refuse foreign aid, expressed by the prime minister of the time, Manmohan Singh. However, there is no such policy, and in fact, it was just a statement made by Dr. Singh.

Since 2004, policies have implicitly or explicitly stated that the government could accept foreign aid during emergencies. The second argument is related to national pride that India no longer requires aid from foreign countries and does not need their charity. This argument is flawed because it is not only emerging countries that require foreign aid, for example, in 2005, the US accepted India's aid for Hurricane Katrina. The third argument is that India is self-sufficient and does not need aid from other countries; it can look out for itself. During emergencies, however, any government would require aid. The fourth argument is that if India accepts foreign aid, it will come with strings attached. The country giving aid to India will ask for something in return, and hence India does not accept foreign aid. The last argument is that money aid will not bring relief (Jacob, 2018).

Figure 8: Possible explanations for India's refusal to accept foreign aid

All these arguments are possible explanations for India's refusal to accept foreign aid. One instance where India refused aid from foreign countries for Kerala after it went through one of the worst floods in over a century (Jacob, 2018). Another instance is India not accepting foreign aid after the earthquake in Kashmir in 2005 (Chaudary, 2018). The refusal to accept foreign aid for any of the arguments given to justify this is not favouring India. Foreign philanthropic contributions aid India and are mainly required during natural calamities and emergencies such as floods and earthquakes. Moreover, no policy says India must not accept foreign aid. It demonstrates that besides policies and laws, ideologies and the political and global climate can also dictate the flow of the philanthropic landscape in India.

4.2 The Foreign Contributions (Regulation) Act

Philanthropic contributions in India can come from foreign sources as well, as seen in the previous subsection. It is regulated by the Foreign Contribution (Regulation) Act (FCRA) which was first introduced in 1976, which was a result of the controversy regarding parliamentary elections using foreign funds (The Institute of Chartered Accountants of India (ICAI), 2015).

The FCRA 1976 states that it regulates "the acceptance and utilisation of foreign contribution or foreign hospitality by certain persons or associations" (The Foreign Contribution (Regulation) Act (FCRA), 1976, p. 3) and ensures the contributions do not negatively affect the national interest. So its intention, besides regulating foreign aid, was to stop the domination or influence of foreign organisations on the Indian

economy (India Development Review (IDR, 2019). It applies to India and its citizens (including NRI's) and companies and corporates registered in India with branches or subsidiaries outside India. As defined by FCRA 1976, a foreign contribution is "donation, delivery or transfer made by any foreign source" (FCRA, 1976, p. 3). The foreign contributions can include any article not given as a gift, any currency (Indian and foreign), and any foreign security (specified in section 2 of Foreign Exchange Regulation Act, 1973).

FCRA 1976 does not allow foreign contributions to be accepted by "candidates for election, correspondent, columnist, cartoonist, editor, owner, printer or publisher of a registered newspaper, Judge, Government servant or employee of any corporation, member of any Legislature, political party or office-bearer thereof" (FCRA, 1976, p. 5). Organisations of a political nature need permission from the central government first before obtaining foreign contributions. Under FCRA 1976, associations with programmes for education, economic, cultural, social, or religious, need to register under the Act to gain foreign contributions (FCRA, 1976). The Act also states that the Central Government can control who gets permission for foreign contributions and prohibit them. Lastly, the Act mentions cases where the penalty can be enforced. Overall, the Act gives the power of decision to the Central Government, which can determine who is allowed to receive foreign contributions. This, in return, points to the fact that the Central Government has power over foreign donations in India, and to an extent, controls the amount of foreign philanthropy entering India. However, this was not as restrictive as the future amendments of this Act become.

FCRA 2010 amendment: Increased constrictions

The Act was amended, and the FCRA 2010 was implemented in 2011 along with the Foreign Contribution (Regulation) Rules (FCRR), 2011. New definitions were added to the FCRA 2010. However, the rules mentioned earlier regarding FCRA 1976 were still more or less the same in FCRA 2010. However, the amendments in FCRA 2010 were more specific in their rules which made them constricting. Initially, the licence was permanent under FCRA; however, it needs to be renewed every five years (Sampath, 2016). It gives control to the centre, allowing them to not renew licences for organisations, that according to them, do not comply with the FCRA.

The FCRA 2010 does not allow an organisation to use foreign contributions to cover fifty per cent of their administrative cost. This constraint may hinder the services of an organisation in the philanthropy sector since foreign aid may be necessary for specific organisations to cover costs. The Act may have put such a restriction to solidify its intention to stop foreign organisations' domination and influence in India. Not allowing the foreign contributor to cover half or more of the administrative costs of an organisation gives them less power over the organisation and thus less influence over the Indian economy and society. However, this also adds to the centre's control as foreign funds have a limit. FCRA also specifies that specific organisations working in education, religion, social, etc. (as mentioned earlier) can register under the Act and accept foreign donations. Although most organisations are involved in activities under at least one of these categories, some organisations may not come under any of these. The FCRA is not clear regarding the application of the Act on organisations that are not involved with the programmes listed (IDR, 2019).

The last significant change that was made was that FCRA 1976 prohibited political parties from getting foreign funds, but in FCRA 2010, the term was changed to 'an organisation of a political nature (Sampath, 2016). It creates loopholes that can be used by political parties to gain foreign funds.

FCRA Bill 2020: A never-ending saga of control

The Foreign Contribution (Regulation) Act, 2010 is amended by the Foreign Contribution (Regulation) Amendment Bill, 2020. The bill introduced quite a few changes. The table below explains the changes and presents a critique.

FCRA- Amendments and Critique - Source: (PRS, 2021)

1. **The change:** A public servant was added to the list of people prohibited from getting foreign donations.

2. **The change:** Foreign contributions can no longer be transferred to anyone else.
Critique: Further restricts the movement of foreign donations, adding to the constraints placed by FCRA.

3. **The change:** In addition to registering and getting prior permission, all office bearers, key functionaries, and directors need to provide their Aadhar numbers.
Further explanation: Further restricts the movement of foreign donations, adding to the constraints placed by FCRA.

4. **The change:** The central government can now control the usage of unutilised foreign contributions as well.
Further explanation: Earlier, the Act allowed anyone who was found guilty of violating provisions of FCRA to use or receive the unutilised and received foreign contribution once it gets approval from the central government.
Critique: This adds to the constraints of the new bill and gives more scope for abuse of power by the central government. It also limits the accountability of the centre since they can make the decisions based on their inquiries; there is no specific obligation to let the other party know of the reasons behind usage limitations.

5. **The change:** Before the renewal of a licence, the government can conduct an enquiry to ensure the person applying has not violated FCRA, not fictitious, and has not been prosecuted for being involved in religious conversion activities, among others
Further explanation: This allows the centre to deny the licence to anyone each time they renew their licence.
Critique: Adds on to the control and power given to the centre.

6. **The change:** The limit of foreign contributions to cover administrative costs reduced from 50% to 20%.
Critique: The foreign funds inflow into the voluntary sector is being further restricted and can hinder the operations of the NGOs and anyone affected by FCRA.

7. **The change:** The period of suspension of registration increased from 180 days to 360 days.
Critique: This allows the suspension of registration for almost a year which can have severe impacts as foreign funds for the person will not be allowed.

Overall, it can be seen that as the amendments are made to FCRA, it becomes more restrictive and increases the control and power the central government has on those affected by FCRA. It can negatively impact foreign funding into the voluntary sector and affect the philanthropic landscape in India.

FCRA reining in foreign Philanthropy in India: Is this the right way?

The government uses FCRA to control foreign contributions. It does this in three ways:

1. Targets and penalises FCRA non-profits that go against the rules of the Act
2. Administrative tightening to eliminate inactive FCRA non-profits
3. Slowed down the prior permission and registration processes (IDR, 2019)

There are various downsides to such restrictions to foreign contributions and their receivers. The new rules that came with FCRA 2010 led to the cancellation of FCRA registration for around four thousand NGOs. The issue was that the FCRA 2010 had clauses that seemed to target human rights organisations. The new rules of FCRA 2010 make it challenging for NGOs to dissent and receive foreign aid. The dissent and protests by these NGOs are classified as a political activity under FCRA and hence led to the cancellation of their FCRA registration. So human rights organisations were the ones that took a hit (Menon, 2012). For the development of society, NGOs and specifically ones that work for human rights are a necessity. Without foreign donations, these organisations may not be able to run the organisation properly. The FCRA 2010 has been criticised as it was the reason behind these cancellations.

The cancellations of FCRA registration for a few large NGOs were forced to be reversed when the case went to the courts. For example, the Delhi high court passed a landmark judgement in response to a writ petition in 2013. The case involved the Ministry of Home Affairs (MHA) and the Indian Social Action Forum (INSAF), which has a network of more than 700 grassroots organisations. MHA had suspended INSAF's FCRA licence because they were 'prejudicial to the public interest' and INSAF's bank accounts were frozen. In their judgment, the high court stated that "if the government decides to suspend an organisation's certificate, it can only do so for reasons recorded in writing, which need to be incorporated in the suspension order itself" (Mehta, 2015). It would ensure that the suspension of licences would be justified to the receivers and achieve transparency in suspensions. The power of decision lies with the Central government; however, they were not forced to justify their decisions before this judgment. This example also demonstrates the possible abuse of power due to no accountability or transparency regarding the cancellations and suspensions under FCRA.

Another example of the abuse of power under FCRA 2010 is the case involving the centre and Greenpeace India in 2015. The centre had blocked about ₹ 1.87 crore fund from Greenpeace's parent organisation in Holland (Mehta, 2015). The high court ordered them to unblock this fund and questioned MHA's uncommon investigations on the NGO. The court also brought up the lack of information regarding the charges against Greenpeace and not giving the organisation time to respond (Mehta, 2015). Once again, the court pointed out the lack of transparency in the charges. In the previous year, Greenpeace was singled out in a report by the Intelligence Bureau claiming it is "a threat to national economic security" (Ranjan & Siddhanta, 2014) and hinders development projects such as coal-related and nuclear-related.

The report also had an unfavourable view regarding foreign-funded NGOs, claiming they negatively impact the economy's development (Ranjan & Siddhanta, 2014). As a result, Greenpeace's FCRA registration was cancelled, and they were suspended, blocking their foreign funds. The reasons for this cancellation are questionable, as done so by the high court in the 2015 case. It further indicates a failure in implementing the policy as the intentions were to ensure the influence of foreign funds was kept to a minimum and to weed out NGOs that misuse their foreign contributions.

Another criticism of FCRA 2010 is that it controls only two per cent of the foreign funds in India. So the voluntary sector should not be singled out for money laundering. It was found in a survey by the Institute of Rural Management, Anand, and found that FCRA is not effective legislation. It controls only \$2 billion, which is only 2 per cent of overall foreign funds in India (Mehta, 2015). The survey also mentions that better monitoring methods need to be implemented instead of curbing (Mehta, 2015).

An article from CUTS International (Consumer Unity & Trust Society) boldly states that any law (such as the FCRA) that interrupts the inward flow of investment which aids economical and social development in the country and leaves the interpretation of it up to the executive needs a thorough, unbiased review and perhaps the removal of it altogether (Mehta, 2015). Since FCRA 2010 does not regulate all the foreign funds that come to the country, it shows bias in regulating foreign contributions, which is limited to the voluntary sector. It indicates that India cannot account for total foreign philanthropy. It creates a gap in data for the same, causing a hindrance to our understanding of the full impact foreign philanthropy has had on the Indian economy and society.

So far, it can be said that the regulation of foreign Philanthropy in India is not the right way and instead has allowed the abuse of the government's power in controlling non-profits. The most recent incident occurred this year where 300 NGOs received a sudden letter claiming that the government "has reasonable cause to believe" that specific rules of FCRA were broken, and they will undergo an audit. There was no clear explanation for the complaint that led to the need for an audit at the NGO. The auditors were picking out Muslim employees and questioning the expenses field concerning them. Another issue brought up at this time was the involvement of politics in NGOs which is not allowed. However, 'politics' is not adequately defined in the law. According to a newspaper article, a Delhi-based accountant said that FCRA was filled with verbal ambiguities. The NGOs that went through audits still have not received their results.

Moreover, the renewal of FCRA registration under the 2020 amendment is just a few months away. The continuous scrutiny NGOs and their employees face due to FCRA is an abuse of power. If this is the case and it continues, perhaps foreign Philanthropy in India would be better off without the FCRA regulations or at least a less restrictive version of it (Subramanian, 2021).

How much of an impact has FCRA made?

With the increase in restrictions with each amendment, critics are worried that the law is now being used as a tool to control non-profit organisations (Centre for Asian Philanthropy and Society (CAPS), 2020). It is a result of the social costs of the rapid development of the economy (CAPS, 2020). Moreover, it looks like FCRA has made a negative impact on foreign Philanthropy in India. Since 2014, 24,000 non-profit organisations' FCRA licenses have been cancelled based on supposed non-compliance with reporting of finances and donations (CAPS, 2020). According to a survey on social delivery organisations in India, 43% of the organisations receiving foreign funds have found fundraising more difficult after the regulatory changes (CAPS, 2020). Another study approximates that foreign funding

has reduced by 40% between 2015 and 2018 (CAPS, 2020). This indicates the adverse impact FCRA's strict regulations have created.

Further data supports the fact that the regulatory nature of FCRA has not created a positive impact in the philanthropy field. Below is a graph for the number of foreign donations from 2009 till 2019 in ₹ 1000 crores.

Figure 9: Amount of foreign donations through FCRA (1000 crore)/ Rupees

Source: (CSIP, 2021)

As the graph shows, the number of foreign contributions fell from 2009-10 to 2010-11. The drop could be due to the increase in cancellations of FCRA registrations of NGOs, leading to a decrease in the number of foreign donations through FCRA. After this year, however, as the trend line shows, there is a gradual increase until 2013-14, which is also the year in which saw the highest amount to foreign contributions. After that, there was a gradual decrease, and the lowest amount of contributions is in the year 2017-18. There is a recovery in the year 2018-19 when the amount of foreign donations increases again. There seems to be no specific trend that can explain the entire process of foreign donations through FCRA.

Figure 10: Percentage of FCRA cancellations on violation/ 2012-2019

Source: (CSIP, 2021)

Next, the graph above shows the number of cancellations of registration under FCRA based on a violation from 2012 to 2019. The highest number of cancellations occurred in 2015, accounting for 52% of the overall cancellations from 2012-19. The number of cancellations for 2010 is not specified; however, one could assume it was high. The year 2017 had the second largest number of cancellations accounting for 25% of the overall cancellations. There is no specific trend that suggests cancellations have increased or decreased with each year. Data for a few years are missing, indicating a lack of sufficient data regarding cancellations under FCRA.

Figure 11: No. of NGOs registered under FCRA / 2009-2019

Source: (CSIP, 2021)

The last graph in figure 11 above shows the number of NGOs registered under FCRA from 2009 to 2019. The trend line shows that the number of registrations of NGOs has been relatively consistent with not many significant changes in the number. The lowest number of registrations was in 2018-19, and the highest was 2011-12. It is interesting to note that the lowest number is in the most recent year. It could be a result of the increasing constraints imposed by FCRA as the years went on.

Conclusion

FCRA has had various criticisms for its restrictiveness and the increased power it gives the central government to control foreign funds. Through the data, no specific conclusions could be made, indicating the lack of public access to foreign philanthropy data or its documentation.

Trends in foreign philanthropy cannot be discovered through the information from FCRA since not all foreign funds in India are regulated by the Act, only around 2%, as mentioned earlier. Nevertheless, the regulatory Act controls the foreign donations made in India to a large extent. It is perhaps creating a negative impact on the flow of foreign funds in India.

4.3 Section 135 of Companies Act 2013

India is the first and only country to introduce mandated corporate social responsibility (CSR) through section 135 of the Companies Act 2013 (Jain et al., 2020). According to the United Nations Industrial

Development Organisation (UNIDO), CSR is a concept where environmental and social issues are incorporated into a company's business operations and relationships with stakeholders (UNIDO, 2021). The mandated CSR in India formalises and mandates corporate philanthropy to a certain extent since it ensures corporates contribute to CSR and hence corporate philanthropy.

Section 135 has specific provisions for CSR in India- a company with a net worth of ₹ 500 crore or more, or turnover of ₹ 1000 crore or more, or net profit of ₹ 5 crores or more, during any financial year, must have a CSR Committee of the Board with three or more directors, of which at least one director must be independent. The responsibilities of this committee are to recommend to the board a CSR policy which comprises of the activities taken on by the company, recommend the expenditure amount of the activities, and occasionally monitor the CSR policy of the company. The board's responsibility is to - approve the CSR policy after taking recommendations from the committee and ensure the company's activities under the CSR policy are undertaken. The board must also ensure that the company spends 2% of the average net profits (made during the preceding three years) each year, following the CSR policy.

Additionally, the amount spent will be on the local areas around where the company operates. Suppose a company fails to spend the mandated CSR amount. In that case, it must provide reasons for not spending the mandated amount of CSR (The Companies Act, 2013).

Companies Act 2017 amendment: Clarity in understanding

The Companies Act was amended in 2017, and provisions under section 135 became clear. The 2013 Act mentioned that a company must have a CSR committee to meet the specified net worth, turnover, or net profit requirements in any financial year. The 2017 Act changes it from 'any financial year' to the 'immediately preceding financial year' (The Institute of Company Secretaries of India, n.d.).

Next, it clarifies the need for an independent director and the minimum number of directors required as two or more. The last clarity that was introduced was regarding 'net profits' and 'average net profits'. The 2013 Act defines net profits and specifies the method needed for calculating net profits; however, it also mentions that 'average net profits' will be calculated. The inconsistency was corrected, and only 'net profits' is used throughout section 135. With more clarity regarding certain aspects of section 135 in the amendment in 2017, regulation may be more efficient now.

The most recent amendment to the Companies Act is in 2021 with Companies (CSR) Amendment rules 2021. The amendment has new definitions for 'administrative overheads', 'CSR', 'CSR policy', and more. The new definitions provide clarity to the terms in the Act, which is beneficial. However, examples could be added to the definitions, such as administrative overheads; specific examples of costs that qualify under the term would provide more clarity (Rishi & Antani, 2021). The responsibilities of the CSR committee have been further clarified in the new amendment, and the board has been given the power to make changes to the committee's proposed plan (Rishi & Antani, 2021). These details are more specific, providing clarity regarding the roles of the board and the CSR committee.

The following significant change is that companies with an average CSR obligation of 10 crore rupees or more in the immediately preceding three financial years need to make an impact assessment of their CSR projects through an independent agency (Rishi & Antani, 2021). This change could encourage meaningful contributions to society since the impact assessment ensures that the CSR project impacts society.

The last but essential amendment is that the boards now have to release the composition of the CSR committee, CSR policy, and CSR projects for public access on their website (Rishi & Antani, 2021). It allows investors and the public to make informed decisions and engage with companies that contribute to society's development. The access given to the CSR information of companies can also benefit research on corporate Philanthropy in India to a certain extent.

Is mandated CSR a necessity?

There have been concerns and critiques regarding section 135 of the Companies Act 2013.

1. Although it is a regulatory act, it does not specify any penalties for failure to abide by the Act's mandated CSR amount (Jana Foundation, n.d.). The problem arises because:
 - a. The board only needs to provide reasons for not abiding.
 - b. There is a penalty for not reporting the reasons, including a fine, and the officer in default could be imprisoned for up to 3 years (Jain et al., 2020). However, since the fine is only for non-reporting, as long as the companies come up with reasons, it allows them to not comply with the mandatory CSR amount specified.

Corporate Philanthropy through the Act is not regulated to the full extent since there is no specified negative outcome for not complying with the compulsory CSR amount.

2. As mentioned earlier, companies need to dedicate 2% of the average net profits to CSR in their local areas. However, the issue here is that state-level disparities occur since certain states may have more companies that contribute CSR to the local regions (Jana Foundation, n.d.).
 - a. For example, Maharashtra and Gujarat have a high number of industrial units. They may have more social development due to the mandated CSR compared to other states.
3. When the economy is in a recession, the lesser privileged people in society need CSR spending. The problem is that:
 - a. During a recession, companies may be incurring losses and may not qualify to abide by the mandated CSR during those years. In this case, the number of companies spending on CSR will reduce, and the vulnerable groups that need higher amounts will not get it.
 - b. Corporate philanthropy then is not reaching targeted groups when they most need it, despite the mandated CSR. In this case, instances of corporates choosing to spend on CSR regardless of the amount specified by the Act would benefit society.

All this leads to questioning the need for the regulatory policy of mandated CSR when corporates can choose to make philanthropic contributions through CSR regardless of the Act. A counter-argument to this is that CSR since the law was implemented, CSR has grown at a rate of around 12% from 2014 to 2018 (CAPS, 2020). Moreover, if every company that came under the Act complied with it, CSR funds could become a total of INR 22,000 crores (CAPS, 2020).

4. The Act specifies certain activities that companies can spend their CSR on, such as heritage and culture and sports promotion. The issue is that:
 - a. Companies may choose to spend the mandated CSR amount on these activities, although they are not pressing issues of society.
 - b. The contributions could be given to more pressing problems such as poverty, malnutrition, and inequality (Jana Foundation, n.d.).

So far, the need for a mandated CSR is not evident since it does not demonstrate how mandated CSR's effects are primarily different from no mandated CSR and giving corporates the freedom to contribute the amount they would like to.

Despite the supposed lack of regulation by the mandated CSR, a survey by KPMG in 2017 showed that the compliance rate of companies was at 95%, and some spent more than the mandated 2%. When looking at these statistics, the mandated CSR seems to be working to a certain extent. Theoretically, for a developing country like India, CSR legislation seems necessary to regulate and encourage CSR by as many companies as possible. However, it has been criticised for its poor measurement of achievements and social impacts and ineffective implementation mechanisms (Jain et al., 2020).

The mandated CSR has also been criticised for its limitation of the scope of CSR activities (Gopalan & Kamalnath, 2015). The Act recognises CSR expenditure only on the specified activities in the Act (Gopalan & Kamalnath, 2015). Although the list is quite diverse, it still limits where the mandated CSR amount can be spent.

Another critique was brought up by Mr Ajit Chaudary, the assistant Vice President at Tata Sons Limited. He said that "it (mandated CSR) was a huge wake-up call. The downside is that it becomes like a tax...The amendments of January 2021 have made it (Companies Act) more tax-like". Mr Chaudary also mentioned that "the law had many positive repercussions as well. It first said what CSR is and what is not CSR...".

Ms Nagma Mulla, the CEO of EdelGive Foundation, said something similar about the mandated CSR. In her words: "The one good thing about CSR, I believe, is that it made philanthropy a board room conversation. Whether people understood it or not, the concept of giving, the reason to give, the mission, and the vision started getting discussed by the most influential people in any company, which I think is good. Many pros and cons came from it, but I think that is one of the strongest things we see".

Considering the critiques and positives mentioned about mandated CSR in India, a few suggestions to improve the Act are: defining CSR clearly, reducing governmental and political interference, and reducing constant changes (Jain et al., 2020). Lastly, suppose the policy is strictly implemented, with proper penalties in place to increase compliance. As mentioned earlier, if all eligible companies strictly abide by the law, CSR funds can amount to around INR 22,000 crores. In that case, a strict implementation may improve the regulation of corporate philanthropy, give the government an idea of the amount of CSR spent on society and its effects, and increase the flow of funds in Corporate Philanthropy. However, , since this is not the case, the need for mandated CSR is still up for debate.

Conclusion

The amendments for the companies Act and CSR regulations have become more apparent as new amendments came in. It has brought clarity regarding CSR rules for companies and can contribute to the understanding and regulating corporate Philanthropy in India. There are both pros and cons to the law, and in an ideal scenario, the law may benefit India.

4.4 Income Tax Act 1961

The following Act that affects Philanthropy in India is the Income Tax Act, 1961. This Act is amended by the Finance Act every year since 1961 and has led to different sections after 1961. The sections that have affected philanthropy are sections- 35AC, 80G, and 12A. The timeline of the introduction of each section in the Act is given in the figure below.

Figure 12: Timeline of the Income Tax Act

Section 80G has tax exemptions for donors donating to trusts and funds registered under the section. Under section 80G of the Income Tax Act, an eligible donation (one to a trust registered under 80G) by donors is qualified for a tax deduction of 50% if the donor is a company (Income-Tax Act, 1961).

The tax deduction for private trusts is determined by taking the total deduction and 10% of the total gross income, whichever amount is lesser, which is the qualifying amount for tax deductions (Taxguru, 2020). In government donations to trusts and funds, 100% of the donated amount is eligible for tax deductions (Taxguru, 2020).

This section provides an incentive for donors to donate to trusts and funds with an 80G certificate. The donated amount is eligible for 50% or 100% tax exemptions (International Center for Not-For-Profit Law, 2020). Hence, section 80G could play a role in encouraging philanthropic contributions to trusts and funds, both private and government ones, because of the tax benefits that come with the donations.

According to a report on Philanthropy in India, individuals see no issue with the limit to tax exemptions on their philanthropic contributions. Individuals have personal motivation and desire when donating to trusts and funds (National Foundation for India (NFI, n.d.). However, the same cannot be said for businesses more affected by tax rates since their decisions are logic-driven (NFI, n.d.).

Next is section 12A which gives the conditions required for the registration of non-profit entities to be eligible for tax exemptions on their income (Income-Tax Act, 1961). Non-profit entities registered under this section are fully exempt from taxes ensuring that no part of the philanthropic donations is taken away as taxes (NFI, n.d.). This section allows for philanthropic donations to reach the targeted audience without any amount being diverted to taxes. It, in turn, may also encourage an increase in donations as they reach the targeted audience and guarantee to a certain extent that the amount donated will impact society.

The last section that affects philanthropic giving is section 35AC which allows tax deductions for the expenditure on eligible projects or schemes (Income-Tax Act, 1961). This section enables corporates and business donors to treat donations to specific organisations as an expenditure and allows for a 100% tax exemption (NFI, n.d.). The tax exemption is allowed only if the donation is given to an organisation whose registration has been approved by the National Committee (Income-Tax Act, 1961). Similar to the earlier sections, this section also encourages donations due to the resulting tax benefits, increasing philanthropic giving in India.

Income Tax Amendments: A boon or a bane?

There were recent amendments made to all the previous sections of the Act. From 2020 onwards, section 12A has become section 12AA and 12AB, which gives the procedure for registration for tax exemptions. In this newly amended section, the time limit for granting registration has been restricted to 5 years. There was no specific period in the earlier section (where registration was valid until cancelled)

(Singhal, 2020; Income-Tax Act, 1961), which means that the registration must be renewed every five years and checked for compliance with the Act before approving the registration. All trusts and institutions earlier registered now need to gain approval and register again after the amendment (Singhal, 2020). This change causes the procedure for registration approval to become longer and delays the process as it needs to be done every five years. However, if executed well, it allows the government to weed out trusts and institutions that do not comply with the Act and are inactive. It could lead to increased confidence in the registered organisations, possibly increasing donations from donors as well.

Next, section 80G has become much more detailed with its provisions in 2021. The new amendment now makes it a requirement for the trust or institution to give a certificate to the donor, which will allow the donor to get tax deductions ("Section 12AB...", n.d.; Income-Tax Act, 1961). It increases the donors' dependency on the trust they donate to ensure they get the certificate. The different procedures may discourage donors from donating because they need to depend on the trust or institution to give a certificate. The burden on the trust also increases as they need to provide certificates of the donated amount to the donors. Lastly, the tax deduction benefits under section 35AC have been removed since March 31st, 2017 (Aulakh, 2021). The incentives to corporates and businesses to donate have been removed, with tax benefits under section 35AC no longer continued. Overall, the amendments make the procedures slower and restrictive, but proper execution may be a boon.

How much of an impact has Income Tax Act made?

Looking at data and graphs regarding the different sections can help further understand the number of tax deductions over the years.

Figure 13 below shows the tax deduction amount for corporates under section 35AC and 80G from 2007 to 2019. After 2017, there is no data for deduction under section 35AC because it was removed from that year onwards.

As the graph in figure 13 shows, the tax deductions under 80G are high in 2007-08 and 2008-09. It can be inferred that the number of donors was also higher during these years, or the of donations was enormous, so the tax deduction amount is also significant. After these years, however, the number of tax exemptions reduced to a large extent and continued to remain low before slowly increasing again from the year 2014-15 onwards.

After 2014-15 the deduction amount gradually increased but was not nearly as high as during 2008-09 and 2007-08. Comparatively, the tax deduction amount under section 35AC is far lower, and the highest amount was in the year 2014-15. However, it was never more than the deductions under section 80G. removing tax exemptions under section 35AC could be that.

Figure 13: Tax deductions for Corporates (Rupees crore) / 2007-2019

Source: (CSIP, 2021)

The following graph in figure 14 shows tax deductions for non-corporates under section 35AC and 80G from 2007 till 2019. As for the earlier graph, here as well, the tax deductions under section 80G are much larger than the tax deductions under section 35AC. Compared to corporates, for non-corporates, the deductions under section 80G remained high throughout most of the years. The low amount of tax exemptions under section 35AC again supports the possibility that this was one reason tax benefits under this section was removed in 2017.

Figure 14: Deductions for Non-corporates (Rupees crore) / 2007-2019

Source: (CSIP, 2021)

Lastly, figure 15 below shows tax deductions for individuals and HUFs (Hindu United Family) under section 80G from 2007 till 2019. It is seen that the highest tax deduction amount was in the year 2018-19 and the second highest in the year 2009-10.

Figure 15: Tax deductions for Individuals/HUFs (Rupees crore) / 2007-2019

Source: (CSIP, 2021)

Conclusion

In conclusion, the sections under the Income Tax Act have become more detailed and more precise as new amendments came in. This allows more efficient regulation of tax deductions and clarifies rules for those affected by the Act.

4.5 The Trusts Act 1882

The Indian Trusts Act 1882 governs private trusts in India and dictates the rules and regulations for their formation and management. There has been an amendment to this Act in 2016 with the Indian Trusts (Amendment) Bill, 2015, which became the Indian Trusts (Amendment) Act, 2016. This amendment brings changes to sections 20 and 20A. Section 20 gives provisions regarding the investment of the trust money and restricts the areas in which trustees can invest to only the prescribed securities. Section 20A also restricts the powers of purchasing redeemable stocks at a premium by the trustees. These two sections have been amended to give trustees more freedom and allow them to invest their trust funds in bonds and securities notified by the government.

This amendment provides more liberty to trustees to handle the funds necessary for their growth in terms of philanthropy. Thus the amendment helps reduce the earlier restrictions on trusts and allows for a smoother flow of funds for trustees, allowing them to choose where to invest ("Lok Sabha passes bill...", 2015; The Indian Trusts (Amendment) Act, 2016).

5. CONCLUSION: WHAT IS THE FUTURE OF PHILANTHROPY IN INDIA?

In summary, the answers found so far are

- Individual and corporate philanthropy is increasing
- The philanthropic money from these two types of philanthropy mainly goes to education, youth, healthcare, and community development
- Regulatory changes for FCRA have been restrictive and negatively impacted foreign philanthropy
- Mandated CSR has both pros and cons: the benefit is that it has made CSR a boardroom conversation, and the downside is that it may not always encourage CSR
- Income Tax Act has become more precise with the regulatory changes, and so has the Trusts Act

The ultimate question of whether these regulations are needed remains since they have both advantages and disadvantages.

The Indian philanthropic sector has a long history, as described throughout the paper, but what lies ahead? How do we get younger generations and others to give more? With the trends observed so far, giving has been increasing in India but will it continue to increase? The next step that can be taken in this field is to bring new ideologies to the sector to improve its efficiency and encourage philanthropy. For example, Mr Manzoor Ghori mentioned that "You have to give, not only give, you have to organise to give".

In the USA, children are trained from an early age to organise an event themselves to raise funds for a cause. A similar regime could be incorporated in the Indian culture of giving, where one must organise to give and not just give. People in the field give many simple ideas to grow philanthropy. There remain many more questions to be asked about this field and many more answers to be found. What lies ahead is investigating the philanthropic field after the pandemic and the recent regulatory changes and looking at ways to improve its efficiency and efficacy in India.

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CENTRE FOR DEVELOPMENT POLICY AND PRACTICE (CDPP)

The Centre for Development Policy and Practice (CDPP) is a research institute that works on development concerns and contemporary public policy challenges.

Working with a team of research professionals and expert consultants, under the guidance of eminent public intellectuals, CDPP conducts research studies, develops policy papers, publishes a peer reviewed quarterly Journal and hosts Conferences, Seminars and Workshops.

CDPP - GOVERNING COUNCIL

1. G. Sudhir is a former IAS officer. He was Chairman of the Commission of Inquiry to study the Socio-economic and Educational conditions of Muslims in Telangana.
2. Amir Ullah Khan is Research Director at CDPP and a Development Economist. He teaches at ISB, IIFT, NALSAR, MCRHRDI and TISS.
3. Neelima Khetan headed the CSR division for companies like Coca-Cola, the Vedanta Group and Hindustan Zinc Limited. She is now visiting fellow at Brookings India
4. Amitabh Kundu has been chairperson of the Post-Sachar Evaluation Committee set up by Ministry of Minority Affairs. Currently, he is chairs a Committee for Swachh Bharat Mission at the Ministry of Drinking Water and Sanitation.
5. Aalok Wadhwa is a management professional with more than three decades of experience working in FMCG, online and social media content, publishing, and retail businesses.
6. Saleema Razvi is a Research Economist at the Copenhagen Consensus Center. She has previously served in organisations like Indian Council for Research on International Economic Relations, Population Foundation of India, and UNICEF.
7. Abdul Shaban is a Professor at Tata Institute of Social Sciences. He has been a member of Post-Sachar Evaluation Committee, Chief Minister's High-Powered Committee on Muslims, Government of Maharashtra; and Sudhir Commission, Telangana.
8. Adeeluddin Syed is a Director at CDPP, and a philanthropist and social worker.
9. Jeemol Unni is a former Director of the Institute of Rural Management, Anand (IRMA) and RBI Chair Professor of Economics at IRMA. She is currently Professor at Ahmedabad University.
10. Rubina Mazhar is a social entrepreneur and Founder of SAFA. SAFA is a self-sustainable organisation working for the socio-economic upliftment of women.

CDPP - RESEARCH TEAM

1. G. Sudhir is Chairman of the Research Team at CDPP, and a former IAS officer.
2. Amir Ullah Khan, Research Director at CDPP, is a former Civil Servant. He has worked with Encyclopedia Britannica, India Development Foundation and the Bill and Melinda Gates Foundation.
3. Netheena Mathews, Senior Fellow (Publications), is also the Managing Editor of the Journal of Development Policy and Practice. She has past experience in Policy Research and Advocacy, Journalism and Academic Publishing.
4. Nahia Hussain, Vice President (Policy Affairs) at CDPP, has worked on diverse issues like Gender Rights, Sustainability, Foreign Policy, and Criminal Justice.
5. Sriram Bhupathiraju, Analyst at CDPP, is an anthropologist with an MPhil from IIT, Hyderabad.
6. Anjana Divakar is Research Associate at CDPP with a Masters in Public Policy from Jindal School of Government and Public Policy. She is Managing Editor of the Journal of Development Policy and Practice.
7. Samia Farheen is research intern at CDPP. She has a triple major in Psychology, Economics and Sociology from Mount Carmel College, Bangalore.
8. Syed Salman Uddin is research assistant at CDPP. He has a degree in mechanical engineering from JNTU.
9. Syed Moin Afroz is Lead Graphic Designer at CDPP. He has been a part of the design industry for a decade now.
10. Ismail Shaikh is an Editorial and Communications intern at CDPP.

SAHAYATA TRUST

Registered in 1996, Sahayata Trust is a not-for-profit non-governmental organization (NGO) based out of Hyderabad, India. Sahayata Trust works with the objective of contributing to the welfare of society by reaching out to the underprivileged and economically weaker sections of India, irrespective of caste, color, gender or faith. We aid and support those in need of basic necessities such as food, healthcare and education, among others.

Sahayata Trust works with a dedicated team, visionary leadership and volunteers pan-India to bring about socio-economic development. Through our efforts, we aim to help the marginalized reach their full potential with quality education, contribute to nation-building as healthy citizens, and have a voice in decisions that affect them, while living and working with dignity.

PLUSTRUST

Vision

A world where all people – specially those from resource poor communities – have the opportunity to create an impact for themselves and others.

Mission

Our mission is to build an Ecosystem to inspire and nurture women and youth as Edupreneurs, Changemakers and Entrepreneurs.

Beliefs And Core Values

We believe that all young people, especially women can be impactful changemakers; investing in them and nurturing them has the potential to create large scale spirals of positive transformation.

Our Values:

Compassion | Equality | Courage(to speak one's mind) | Dialogue | Freedom to innovate and experiment

Our Offering

The Plustrust micro-Incubation process helps changemakers and social entrepreneurs, especially rural women, located in resource poor communities to refine, define, test and develop their ideas for change. Our network of specially trained Anchors offer localized support to entrepreneurial ideas at a nascent stage. It empowers women and improves quality and spread of basic services like education, skill development, healthcare and wellbeing.

The Plustrust Virtual Adda in Udaipur and the Plustrust Caring Friends Adda in Ujjain bring together the inspiration, Knowledge and skill for nurturing these sprouts.

The CDPP brings out a monthly working paper based on the research work being carried out here. These are published on our website www.cdpp.co.in and sent to a select group for review, comments and critique.

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